

ON THE SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF ABDULLA KODIRIY'S NOVEL *BYGONE DAYS*

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Abstract. *This article examines the socio-philosophical essence of Abdulla Kodiriy's novel Bygone Days through a renewed analytical perspective shaped by the intellectual context of New Uzbekistan. The study focuses on Kodiriy's personality, spiritual and intellectual maturity, and the objective and subjective factors that influenced the formation of his social, philosophical, artistic, and aesthetic views. Using comparative, historical-logical, creative, and systematic methods, the article argues that Bygone Days is not merely a historical novel about Uzbek life, but a profound literary-philosophical work addressing individual freedom, rational life, national awakening, and resistance to oppression. Special attention is paid to the symbolic roles of Otabek, Kumush, Yusufbek Hoji, and Uzbek Oyim in revealing the conflict between enlightenment and ignorance, freedom and dependence, progress and medieval traditions. The article concludes that Kodiriy's socio-philosophical ideas remain relevant for contemporary society.*

Keywords: *jadidism, personality, individual freedom, faith, truthfulness, society, Eastern traditions, rational life.*

Introduction

The important changes taking place in the socio-political, spiritual, and moral life of our country during the last four or five years require a deeper understanding of the place and role of the individual in the life of society and the development of the country, as well as recognition of the fact that societies are governed by personalities and states are governed by politicians. Indeed, the new worldview of the emerging New Uzbekistan has created favorable conditions for an objective and truthful scholarly study of the heritage, life, and stages of development of our great ancestors.

During the last hundred years of the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan, the sole dominance of the state over the whole life of society, that is, state totalitarianism, continuously restricted the individual and their freedoms and hindered democratic reforms. The fact that the individual is essentially called upon to solve rationally the complex problems faced by society requires scientific substantiation of Uzbekistan's need for personalities and, for this purpose, the orientation of our education and upbringing system toward the individual [1].

The world-famous English thinker Arnold Toynbee, in his theory of civilization, proved with historical and logical arguments that a creative minority is a factor accelerating historical development. At turning points in historical development, crises can be overcome only if the creative minority, that is, personalities, have the opportunity, ability, and potential to give a worthy "Response" to the "Challenge." Otherwise, they will inevitably leave the stage of history and be condemned to nonexistence [2].

At turning points in the development of society, creative personalities strive to understand more deeply the essence of a changed era, to draw lessons from its mistakes and shortcomings by

looking back at the past, to comprehend the essence and meaning of the philosophy of history, to see the prospects of socio-spiritual development, and to educate individuals capable of struggling against oppression and tyranny through enlightenment. One such great thinker was Abdulla Kodiriy (1894–1938).

As one of the leading representatives of the Jadid movement, which entered the arena of the struggle for freedom in Turkestan in the mid-nineteenth century, Abdulla Kodiriy was a living witness and active participant in the important changes that took place in the socio-political and spiritual life of our region at the beginning of the twentieth century, especially after the February bourgeois revolution of 1917. He sensed the shadow of the despotic regime's mass repressions against liberty, freedom, and independence, and under the shadow of these horrors he used the favorable possibilities of fiction to advance the ideas of liberty and national independence.

Although his novel *Bygone Days*, from the outside, may appear to be “a historical novel from Uzbek life,” or today's version of *Tohir and Zuhra*, *Four Dervishes*, *Farhod and Shirin*, and *Bahromg'ur*, in essence it is a literary-philosophical work on an extremely important socio-political theme.

Methods

In the research process of this article, in studying the laws and characteristics of the formation of a creative personality, we used the methods of comparative analysis of the old and new periods of Uzbekistan's history, historicity and logicity, creativity, and systematic analysis. Through these methods, we attempted to substantiate that the creation of Abdulla Kodiriy's masterpiece was connected with the historical necessity of liberating the peoples of Turkestan at the beginning of the twentieth century.

Degree of Study of the Topic

During the past hundred years, many studies have been created that are devoted to discovering the secret and power of Abdulla Kodiriy's genius. However, from the 1960s until 2017, researchers did not express any opinion about why Abdulla Kodiriy's masterpiece, *Bygone Days*, became the reason for his being accused as an “enemy of the people.”

With the arrival of a new stage in the development of Uzbekistan, literary scholars' approaches to this topic changed.

As the well-known literary scholar Omonullo Madaev emphasized, “Throughout his entire creative career, in the novels, dramatic works, stories, feuilletons, letters, and scholarly works he created, Abdulla Kodiriy worked as a historian, ethnographer, philosopher... and most importantly, as a master of classical and beautiful words” [3].

As the well-known literary scholar and Hero of Uzbekistan Ibrohim G'afurov emphasized in his foreword entitled “The Image of Kodiriy” to the five-volume edition, Abdulla Kodiriy, with his entire being, is “a symbol of struggle, conscience, and freedom” [4].

Therefore, in recent scholarly literature we have not encountered scientific works that approach the essence of Abdulla Kodiriy's novel *Bygone Days* from a new socio-philosophical perspective.

Research Results

Until 1924–1926, Abdulla Kodiriy continued the traditions of the Jadid writers contemporary to him, such as Behbudiy, Abdulla Avloniy, Fitrat, Cho'lpon, and Hamza Hakimzoda. In 1915 he created the four-act drama *The Unhappy Bridegroom*, the novel *Juvonboz*, and the feuilleton *Shodmarg*. In these works, the writer, as an enlightener, a people-loving author, and a creator struggling against backwardness, ignorance, lack of knowledge, and lack of faith,

sought through enlightenment, theater, and humor, that is, comedy, to awaken hatred toward the vices in the everyday life of his contemporaries and to encourage them to live rationally.

After studying at the Institute of Journalism in Moscow in 1924 and acquiring thorough knowledge of literary trends, methods of artistic creativity, and various philosophical currents characteristic of advanced European literature, fundamental positive changes undoubtedly occurred in Abdulla Kodiriy's philosophical, scientific, artistic, and aesthetic views. The first product of these changes was the feuilleton *Collected Words*, published in the journal *Mushtum* in 1926, which caused radical changes in the fate of the writer.

The initiation of a criminal case against Abdulla Kodiriy and the speech delivered during his trial reveal, first, that in Abdulla Kodiriy's first confrontation as a personality with the existing government and policy over the issue of individual freedom, the totalitarian and despotic regime was clearly opposed to the individual, free thought, and liberty. Because of tyranny, his close creative colleagues, including Akram Oripov, editor-in-chief of *Mushtum*, Ziyoy Said, and others, betrayed him.

Second, he rejected the proposals of his closest friends to leave temporarily for another country and survive the mass repression. Kodiriy wanted to prove that he was absolutely innocent and thereby to prove the injustice and cruelty of the brutal regime. Indeed, personalities are always people of faith, truthful and sincere, and people who wish goodness for others. Abdulla Kodiriy was such a personality.

According to Arnold Toynbee's teaching, as soon as personalities are formed, they become unlike the people around them. For them, a critical approach to reality, not personal interest but the interests of the people and society, and the struggle to liberate the people from slavery, dependence, and ignorance become a life principle. Contemporaries reject the personality; alienation occurs between the personality and the social environment, the people, and the society that brought them up.

Great personalities, in order to overcome this "alienation," turn to the spiritual, psychological, and aesthetic world of the people to whom they belong, to the "dirtiest and ugliest" events of the past, and, through historical facts and evidence, try to show the misled people and society the most correct and just path. They seek to glorify all positive qualities and virtues that can serve national development and to expose before their contemporaries the pessimistic face of ignorance, backwardness, oppression, and tyranny. A creative personality who has become unlike others through progressive views temporarily departs from society and the people with their ideas and views. However, they return to the bosom of their people with new qualities and virtues. In other words, the alienation of great creative personalities such as Abdulla Kodiriy, Abdulla Qahhor, Abdulla Oripov, and Shavkat Rahmon from their people, that is, their difference from others, and their "return" to their people is a general sociological law and is a product of the new philosophical worldview being firmly established in New Uzbekistan.

Abdulla Kodiriy understood well that fiction is an inseparable component of the spiritual life of the Uzbek people, a specific form of their way of thinking and their knowledge of the essence of the world. Through artistic images and devices, he dared to philosophically analyze the reasons why the peoples of Turkestan fell under the oppression of tsarist colonialism, to expose the ugly customs of medievalism, and to prepare the broad masses spiritually and psychologically for the struggle for national independence.

In order to comprehensively substantiate the tragic consequences that spiritual poverty, loyalty to ugly traditions, the suppression of individual freedom, ignorance, and lack of education

can bring to the fate of an entire nation, the great artist chose his theme “from the past, from recent bygone days, from the later ‘khanate times,’ which were the dirtiest and darkest days of our history.”

The author leads the reader into the world of spiritual and psychological experiences, ideological-political views, and moral perspectives of the highest and most influential stratum of society: owners, capital holders, and officials, who were directly responsible for the fate of society and capable of determining the socio-political environment in society. He assigns a responsible social function to each character of the work and embodies his ideological intention under the name given to each of them.

In particular, Otabek is depicted as a brave, virtuous, and perfect human being who has committed himself to the struggle for individual freedom and the development of the homeland and who has decided to create his own destiny with his own hands. Otabek’s submission to the desires of his mother, Uzbek Oyim, and his condemnation to lack of freedom and dependence are shown as the spiritual crisis of an entire freedom-loving nation, the triumph of ignorance, and the trampling of the homeland under the feet of enemies.

Uzbek Oyim is the symbol of ignorant and uneducated Uzbek women who clung with all their might to medieval traditions, who were “half-baked,” who were capable of making even such a wise and knowledgeable husband as Yusufbek Hoji submit to their wishes and desires, and who opposed individual freedom with all their strength. She is a symbol of those who create wise, virtuous, freedom-loving, and progressive children such as Otabek and then strangle them with their own hands.

The fundamental reasons why the main heroes of Abdulla Kodiriy’s masterpiece, Yusufbek Hoji, Otabek, and Kumush, are the same as the creative personality Abdulla Kodiriy himself are also connected with the evolution of the writer’s formation as a personality. The birth of *Bygone Days* was undoubtedly connected with the maturation of the creative personality.

During the last hundred years, thousands of studies have been created that are devoted to discovering the secret and power of Abdulla Kodiriy’s genius. However, from the 1960s until 2017, researchers could not say a single word about why Abdulla Kodiriy’s masterpiece, *Bygone Days*, became the reason for his being accused as an “enemy of the people.” The reason is that Soviet ideology and policy throughout its entire history were opposed to the individual, their freedoms, and especially to thinking differently. It was impossible to know and acknowledge this truth, not only under the former Soviet despotic regime, but also during the years of national independence in Uzbekistan under a political administration that sought to build a “strong state” and expelled progressive, faithful personalities from the country or imprisoned them.

Abdulla Kodiriy showed that the guides of society and the people were not uneducated and poor workers and peasants, but entrepreneurial, intelligent, educated, wise, and creative personalities. By doing so, he exposed the ugly face of the dark forces that hindered the sincere and pure love of Otabek and Kumush, Anvar and Ra’no, and their struggle for their own freedom: the backward and ignorant political administration system of medievalism and the ugly customs and superstitions contrary to sound reason.

In order to comprehensively substantiate the tragic consequences that spiritual poverty, loyalty to ugly traditions, the suppression of individual freedom, ignorance, and lack of education can bring to the fate of an entire nation, the great artist chose his theme “from the past, from recent bygone days, from the later ‘khanate times,’ which were the dirtiest and darkest days of our history.”

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In the images of Mirzakarim Qutidor, Oftob Oyim, Kumushbibi, Hasanali, and Usta Olim, the writer depicted freedom-loving and progressive forces that were nevertheless weak and helpless before medieval traditions.

Yusufbek Hoji, Uzbek Oyim, Otabek, and Hasanali were members of one family, one social environment. This household was a small symbol of all Turkestan. The spiritual environment in this household was determined and governed by Uzbek Oyim. She was the true mistress of this household. That is why the wise Yusufbek Hoji did not consider it necessary to consult with his wife, Uzbek Oyim, on any matter.

"Yusufbek Hoji had a strange habit," writes A. Kodiriy. "He would not sit and talk for a long time not only with his wife, but with the household in general..."

After making the person speaking to him look into his mouth for some time, if he agreed, he would say 'good'; if he did not understand the matter, he would say 'well'; if he disagreed, he would say 'not right'; and if the matter was very disagreeable to him, he would merely smile and say nothing more, and even if he did speak, he would not go beyond three or four words" [4].

In the image of Yusufbek Hoji, Abdulla Kodiriy embodied the thoughtfulness and wisdom of the ancient East, and in the image of Uzbek Oyim, he embodied the dominance of Eastern traditions and their weak, fragile, and pitiable aspects. Uzbek Oyim was not only a blessed mother who created such a wise, virtuous, and brave person as Otabek, but at the same time she was also an extremely cruel and powerful force that vigorously promoted to her child all the vices of the dark and dirty past, such as polygamy, dependence, and obedience.

Her cruelty and stubbornness were so great that she did not care at all that such a wise, innocent, and beautiful angel as Kumushbibi was poisoned and killed by Zaynab, and she did not regret that she herself was first of all the cause of it. Kumushbibi never let Fuzuli's divan leave her hand; she was truly enlightened, wise, and beautiful. She is a bright symbol of the beautiful future capable of illuminating Otabek's household with knowledge and enlightenment and calling it to goodness. That is why, in the eyes of the great artist, the poisoning of Kumushbibi was the poisoning of the future.

Otabek was the leading intellectual, progressive, and freedom-loving son of his time. At the very beginning of the work, when introducing the reader to Otabek, the son of Yusufbek Hoji, the writer places special emphasis on these qualities and, through his language, shows how unsuitable the political administration in backward and impoverished Turkestan was.

While visiting the house of Ziyoy Shohichiy, Otabek tells how he had been to Russian cities for trade reasons:

“When I saw the administrative cities of the Russians, I was forced to admit that our own administration was exactly like a toy... If our administration continues with its present disorder, I could not imagine what would become of us. While I was in Shamay, if only I had wings, I would fly to my homeland, descend straight into the khan’s palace, explain one by one the administrative laws of the Russians, and if the khan listened to my petition and wrote a decree to the whole land, ordering that the Russian administrative order be adopted as a model, I too would see my own people on the same level as the Russians within a month... But when I returned to my homeland, I saw that my thoughts and desires in Shamay had been sweet dreams. Here there was no one to listen to me. Even if there were, they discouraged me by saying, ‘Will these khans listen to your dream? Will these beks implement it?’ At first I did not believe their words, but later I realized that they had spoken the truth. Indeed, in a graveyard, who would hear the call to prayer, ‘hayya ‘alal-falah’ — ‘come to salvation?’” [5].

Yes, Turkestan, which had become a graveyard, had sunk into the swamp of ignorance and was humiliated under the feet of enemies, needed Otabeks. Otabek’s sincere love for Kumushbibi from Margilan, he who had committed himself to giving life to dead and senseless Turkestan, is depicted not simply as a love adventure, but as a struggle for the freedom of the homeland through individual freedom and liberty.

Otabek was a perfect human being capable of creating his own destiny with his own hands. In this matter, it did not even occur to him to consult with his parents and obtain their consent. Yusufbek Hoji deeply felt in his heart the intelligence, feelings, dreams, and hopes of his son Otabek, respected his personality, and for that reason Otabek’s marriage from Margilan did not upset him; on the contrary, it pleased him. This was Abdulla Kodiriy’s ideal. In the view of the great artist, individual freedom and the independence of the homeland are inseparably connected with the freedom of sincere human love. Therefore, in the work, the struggle of Otabek and Kumushbibi for love is presented against the background of the merciless struggle between the new and the old, light and darkness, progress and backwardness.

In this struggle, the wise Yusufbek Hoji, who could have played a decisive role, ultimately obeys the will of his wife Uzbek Oyim and is forced to persuade Otabek to marry for a second time.

“After Uzbek Oyim entered, Yusufbek Hoji remained thinking for some time. Uzbek Oyim kept looking at her husband impatiently. After sitting silently for quite a while, Hoji began to speak gently:

‘My son, whether you have heard it or not, in any case, we have done something concerning you...’

Otabek, of course, knew about ‘what they had done or intended to do.’ Even so, he pretended not to know:

‘What wise people do regarding their sons, of course, cannot be improper,’ he said.

At this answer of his son, Hoji looked down at the ground and did not know what to say in reply.”

Abdulla Kodiriy does not comment on this situation. According to Eastern etiquette, until Hoji finished speaking, Otabek had to look down silently, obey his parents without question. But this does not happen. When Otabek, with high manners and humility, reminds him that Eastern

etiquette is contrary to reason, Yusufbek Hoji inwardly feels that his son is right, and silence begins.

“Again silence fell between them. Uzbek Oyim could not understand the meaning of this silence. After sitting and looking for a while, as if her heart became troubled, she said:

‘We have betrothed you to the daughter of Olim Ponsodboshi... Now we wanted to consult with you about the wedding...’

Otabek said nothing to his mother and looked meaningfully at his father. Hoji, with an embarrassed expression, said, ‘Yes, that is so’” [6].

In portraying Yusufbek Hoji as a wise father and a father who supports individual freedom, A. Kodiriy shows, on the one hand, that although Yusufbek Hoji was not at all opposed to his son’s marriage from Margilan, and on the contrary approved it, on the other hand, even though he admitted that the wishes and desires of Uzbek Oyim, who was uneducated and a slave of customs, were contrary to reason, he was helpless to reform her. Through this, the writer wanted to show that the elite stratum of the Middle Ages was not an example for the common people, but was subordinate to them.

“My son, we have no sign of hope other than you. All the dreams and desires we have in this world depend only on you. We thank Almighty God thousands of times that you became intelligent and sensible, unlike the children of others; even if we cannot be proud of you as others are, we believed that through you we would not suffer shame. Especially your mother’s hopes that she would experience through you increased more and more. Today your mother kneels before you, and for your mother’s sake I too intervene and ask you: since you married according to your own wish, may your wife be blessed for you. The wish of parents who claim to be intelligent, of course, would be nothing other than this. At the same time, one person who is the cause of your existence wishes to experience one dream and desire through her child during her lifetime... Whether you grant her this wish or not, the choice is again yours.

...Yusufbek Hoji did not say the above words dryly and without foundation, but stated to some degree the pillars and basis of this life, and Otabek heard this as a son of that environment. The truth is that he did not possess the strength necessary to oppose the law spoken by his father; therefore, the result of weakness was silence” [7].

“Otabek agreed to the wish of his parents, in his own expression, as a lifeless statue” [8].

This consent was the submission of freedom before slavery and obedience, the beginning of the tragedy of love that symbolized a national tragedy, the sinking of Turkestan, loyal to medieval morality and traditions, into the swamp of backwardness and ignorance, and finally the loss of its independence.

Discussion

In a land where dependence and ignorance ruled, it was inevitable that unfortunate women such as Zaynab would fall into the whirlpool of the environment created by Uzbek Oyims and lose their reason.

From such a painful, pitiable, and tragic fate in *Bygone Days*, Abdulla Kodiriy arrives at the following philosophical conclusion: a country that suppresses individual freedom, preserves medieval morality and traditions, and regards slavery and dependence as virtues will inevitably lose its independence, be trampled under the feet of enemies, and be humiliated. At the end of the work, Otabek, who sacrificed freedom and liberty for the wishes of his parents and lost his wings, dies in the struggle against the Russian invaders; that is, the destruction of Turkestan’s independence confirms this conclusion.

Through this, the writer drew attention to the fact that not only the despotic regime but also the customs of medievalism contrary to sound reason, ignorance, poverty, and the lack of education among women were causes of the suppression of individual freedom.

Conclusion

Fiction plays a very important role in solving the complex socio-political, spiritual, and moral problems faced by society through rational, enlightened, and civilized means. It should be emphasized that only when the personality of the creator is formed does literature become a weapon stronger than the atom and prepare people for the struggle for freedom and democracy.

Therefore, the socio-political, spiritual, and moral problems faced by the peoples of Turkestan at the beginning of the twentieth century gave rise to the great representatives of the Jadid movement. Abdulla Kodiriy, who understood that the peoples of Turkestan were struggling against the ugly customs of medievalism and that the inhuman ideology and policy of Bolshevism were directed against the individual and their freedoms, enriched the Jadid movement with new ideas and content. In his masterpiece *Bygone Days*, he expressed with great skill that ignorance, backwardness, oppression, and tyranny cannot be overcome without firm faith, religious and secular knowledge, a pure heart, and love.

The high socio-philosophical ideas advanced in this work retain their significance and relevance today, and we consider it necessary to study this topic comprehensively.

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